

Hydro-Geomorphic Characteristics of Seasonal Valleys of Gash and Nyala: Potentialities for Rural Development in Semi-Arid Sudan

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Abstract

Hydro-Geomorphic Characteristics of Gash and Nyala seasonal valleys were examined to portray their hydrological behavior which is proficiently potential to sustain water harvesting programs for rural development in semi arid Sudan. Data sources were results of field work carried out by TNO-DGV Institute of Applied Geosciences-Netherlands and National Water Corporation of Sudan, Gash's satellite image provided by Geological Research Authority of Sudan, relevant research done there and GIS analysis of recent satellite imageries of the two valleys. The research adopted descriptive, analytical and derivational approaches. Results depicted that, geomorphological characteristics of Gash and Nyala valleys are almost identical and although they differ in geographic locations, they are both influenced by the Intertropical convergence Zone (ITCZ) and Indian Ocean monsoons which determine the initiation of their annual flooding. They are of mountainous sources, flashy with huge annual discharge and are typically similar in their hydrological behavior. They endanger Kassala and Nyala regional towns and their geographic neighborhood to floods disasters; however the two valleys are potential to contribute into sustainable rural community development by adoption of appropriate water harvesting programs. The research recommended improvement of hydrological recording and estimates, geomorphic controls and precipitation estimate to enhance water harvesting programs and reducing vulnerability of flood disasters.

Key words: geomorphic characteristics, flashy valley, hydrological behavior, hydro-potentiality, water harvesting, rural development

Introduction

Sudan is virtually striving to optimize its natural resources to speed on economic growth, ease political instability, and enhance population growth and to step into the millennium. These natural resources are varied, among which are the seasonal valleys which own abundant amounts of annually discharged waters. These valleys are mostly of mountainous origin, flashy with extremely high discharge, and are sources of disaster vulnerability. Their hydrological behaviors are controlled by their own geomorphic characteristics and nature of precipitation. "Their hydrologic regime is characterized by high variability in temporal and spatial rainfall distributions, flash floods, absence of base flow in most cases, and high rates of evapotranspiration" (Aboubaker et al. 2019). This research aimed to show these characteristics, as exemplified by Gash and Nyala seasonal valleys, in order to build for rural development in semi arid Sudan via water harvesting programs and reduction of flood disasters.

Theoretical background

Rainfall events in semi arid areas are in general of short duration and high intensity and often characterized by a large degree of spatial heterogeneity (Pilgrim et al., 1988; Wheeler et al., 1991; Martinez-Mena et al., 1998; Lázaro et al., 2001; Wheeler, 2008). These characteristics are even more pronounced in regions with topographic complexity such as mountain ranges (Wilson et al. 2004). Due to the spatial variability of rainfall, runoff is frequently localized while runoff generated in some parts of the catchment may later re-infiltrate and thus do not contribute to runoff at the outlet of the catchment. Runoff may re-infiltrate in the bottom of a valley into a bed of alluvial sediments or become overland flow that may be lost as infiltration into fractured bedrock of channels (Hughes 1995). The infiltrating discharge water contributes to groundwater recharge and the associated groundwater flow in the river valley sediments.

River discharge is the final outcome of a large number of vertical and horizontal flow processes within the whole catchment of the discharge observation point. In semi-arid regions the characteristics of the river flow can be classified as perennial that is flowing all the year; seasonal where flowing only occur in part of the

year or ephemeral with extreme flow variability ranging from no flow to flash flood during storms (Lerner et al., 1990). In this region also, discharge appearing in the upstream parts of the river system may gradually diminish during migration in the river system. This is due to infiltration into the river bed and eventually the flow in the river may disappear completely. Also, overland flow in semi arid areas is categorized into, Hortonian-type of runoff and saturation excess overland flow type, according to the mechanisms responsible for its generation. In the Hortonian-type of runoff high rainfall events exceed the infiltration capacity of the soil and thus leads to surface runoff. (Pilgrim et al. 1988, Hughes 1995). The other type of overland flow occurs when rain falls on land where the subsurface is saturated, which may arise during a rainy period in the bottom of the valley. Another common characteristic is that discharge appearing in the upstream parts of the river system may gradually diminish during migration in the river system due to infiltration into the river bed and eventually the flow in the river may disappear completely. Only during flash floods the river may discharge to the sea. This is particularly true for semi-arid regions where recharge may be as low as 1% of the precipitation (Bouwer, 1989). Furthermore recharge usually only occurs in limited areas and generally it is non-existent or negligible over much of the semi-arid landscape e.g. at hill slopes. Recharge may occur by various mechanisms, mainly as direct infiltration in flat areas or infiltration from river beds. Additionally, in some formations the excess precipitation is subsequently routed through fractures before discharging into the river or the alluvial material of the lower plains. Finally the infiltration capacity is also high around vegetation, and conversely, vegetation may only grow where the infiltration capacity is relatively high (Pilgrim et al., 1988).

Evapotranspiration is controlled by several factors such as meteorological conditions; characteristics of the surface; canopy; and soil characteristics. In semi arid regions also, evaporation from bare soil assumes a greater importance relative to transpiration from plants, due to the larger area of bare soil and the frequency of small rainfall events which allow bare soil to return water to the atmosphere without major pathway impedance (Pilgrim et al. 1988). In such regions evapotranspiration captures most of the water entering the soil, and recharge occurs only at extreme rainfall events (Pilgrim et al., 1988). As a result of the spatial variability of landscape characteristics such as geology, topography, soils, land use and vegetation, evapotranspiration will likewise exhibit a spatial variation (Güntner et al. 2004). For hilly and mountainous catchments with a relatively sparse vegetation cover and subject to high rainfall intensities overland flow generation is frequently occurring (Wheater, 2008). This region's recharge of aquifers may be as low as 1% of the precipitation (Bouwer 1989) and usually occurs in limited areas and generally it is non-existent or negligible over much of the semi-arid landscape.

In semi-arid and arid areas, rain water and flood water harvesting came up in interest in recent decades due to insufficient sources of pumped ground water, reservoirs and streams to meet human and animal demand for water (Prinz 2002). Water harvesting techniques harvest and concentrate rainwater and consequently could increase soil moisture and yields (Mugabe 2004). Infield water harvesting for improved crop yield in semi-arid regions of Zimbabwe has been used to adapt to changing climate since climate change increased vulnerability of crop failure in such areas (Nyamadzawo et al. 2013). In semi arid Southern African Development Community which is overpopulated and environmentally fragile there are a number of traditional and new and adapted techniques for water harvesting which aim to alleviate the limiting crop production factors (Kronen 1994). In India, several techniques of water harvesting are used in its semi arid parts for centuries to protect water supplies and to increase agricultural production, and they have been recently promoted (Batchelor et al. 2002).

Material and methods

Study valleys

Gash valley, located at $36^{\circ} 15' - 36^{\circ} 30' E$, and $15^{\circ} 15' - 15^{\circ} 45' N$, is a seasonal stream (valley) flowing from late June to October and originates in the Eritrean highlands (Figure1). When entering the Sudan, the Gash changes from a westerly direction to northerly direction and attains its characteristic appearance of a wide shallow stream with a sandy bed and extensive flood plains on either side as far as el Sabeel/ Wad Sherefei where north of that the Gash Valley tends to widen and further north it fans out into an inland delta (ELKirail et al. 2008).

Figure 1: satellite image of Gash valleys showing source, direction and delta
 Source: GRAS, Geological Research Authority of Sudan, 2010

Nyala valley, located at $24^{\circ} 30' - 25^{\circ} 15' E$, and $11^{\circ} 45' - 12^{\circ} - 45' N$, is also a seasonal stream where its upper limit of the catchment lies near the foot of Jebel Merra (Figure 2). Thus the drainage system does not extend onto the slopes of Jebel Merra, in contrary to the neighboring catchments of Wadi Amer and Wadi Bulbul, but is situated in the piedmont area (Lebon and Robertson 1961). The two main branches of Nyala Valley join at Domai, about 8 km upstream from Nyala town.

Figure 2: satellite image of Nyala valley showing source and direction
 Source: GRAS, Geological Research Authority of Sudan, 2010

Data sources and methods

The satellite image (Figure 1) provided by Geological Research Authority of Sudan (ND 73 A- Sudan Worksheet 1:250000 TM7/TM4 TM1) was interpreted to obtain some of the Gash valley’s geomorphic characteristics. Hydrologic data for Gash’s was obtained from Ground Water and Valley Directorate and relevant fieldwork carried out by TNO-DGV et al. (1982). Studies on channel fill and sheet flood facies sequences in the Gash valley were from Abdullatif’s research (1989), and data on regional ground water

flow of Gash were from Elkirail et al. (2008), while data on ground budget were from El Tom et al (2010) and were used to obtain hydrologic and ground water data for Gash. A recent satellite image of Gash valley, based on DEM 90 USGS was processed by GIS Arc-Map 10.5 to produce ordering of Gash's basin. Geomorphic data for Nyala valley was obtained from Lebon and Robertson (1961), TNO-DGV et al. (1982) and Figure 2, and additionally a recent satellite image based on DEM 90 USGS was processed by GIS Arc-Map 10.5 to produce ordering and lengths of Nyala's basin. Hydrological data for Nyala valley was taken from technical report of TNO-DGV et al. (1985). There were no old continuous records of discharge for Nyala valley similar to that of Gash valley. Relevant Meteorological data for both valleys was from Sudan's meteorological Department and some relevant studies.

Geomorphological characteristics of the Gash Valley

The basement complex represents the oldest rock units in Gash Valley area. The area is then subjected to a period of extensive erosion that reduced the area to a peneplain. The main outcrops of the basement are the granitic biotitic gneisses of sedimentary origin of J. Kassala, and J. Mukram which rise on the plain, and in other places the basement complex was covered with Tertiary-Quaternary deposits (ELKirail et al. 2008). The Gash valley's total catchment area is about 21000 km². In width it varies between 100 m and 800 m. The flood plains may attain a width of as much as 1,000 m on either side of the river bed. Topography is flat to slightly rolling in the Gash- delta, with a gentle sloping towards the north-west. Elevation is a little more than 500 m above mean sea level in the south-east to less than 450 m above mean sea level in the north-west. Just east of Kassala town the topographical features are dominated by two mainly north-south oriented inselbergs of which Jebel Kassala, with an elevation of 1,346 m above mean sea level forms the highest top. The Gash valley basin is filled by the Quaternary alluvial deposits, unconformably overlying the basement rocks. The alluvial deposits are composed mainly of unconsolidated layers of gravel, sand, silt, and clays. The clay of the plain overlies the basement complex, Cretaceous sedimentary series and Tertiary lavas. Detailed facies analysis of the River Gash fluvial sediments has revealed a channel-fill and sheet-flood sequences. It seems that each sequence type is produced by specific depositional event, and both sequences represent two-end members for group of mixed sequences. The facies and sequences show rapid lateral variability, and they merge and interfinger with each other. They also show partial to complete modification due to subsequent floods and stage variation.

The clay of the plain is usually found above the river flood plain east and west of alluvial deposits. It consists of laminated loose to compacted clay, silt and sandy silt. Its thickness ranges from few meters to about 20 meters along the west side of alluvial deposits. The alluvial deposits were formed by the action of Gash Valley during the flood seasons. The coarse material of sand and gravel deposits are located upstream and the finer material of clay deposits downstream. The thickness of alluvial deposits upstream is about 30 meters and reach up to 70 meters downstream. They are composed of intercalating beds of unconsolidated coarse to fine-grained gravel, sand, silt and clay. The gravel is composed mostly of angular to subangular quartz pebbles; however the volcanic, felspathic and granitic gravels are present. The sand is mostly composed of quartz; however, felspathic micaceous and volcanic sand are present. The aquifer is unconfined and is laterally bounded by the impermeable Neogene clays (Eltom et al. 2010). The Gash aquifer is composed of heterogeneous sequence of layers which is dominated by coarse sand, gravel, clayey sand and silts (El-Krail et al. 2008). Gash valley stream ordering (Figure3) reflects an operating dendritic network in the upper and lower reaching. First order and second order have formed on steep slopes of mountains in Eritrea (Ethiopian plateau). They are the headwater valleys, and also, could include third order valleys as headwater streams. Fourth order could be medium valleys, characterized by less steep and flow more slowly, but tend to have larger volumes of runoff and debris as it collects them from the smaller waterways flowing into them.

Figure3: Gash ordering
 Source: GIS Arc-Map 10.5 based on DEM 90 USGS

Geomorphological characteristics of Nyala Valley

Nyala Valley's geology of the catchment (Figure 4) is composed of the quartzite/gneiss formations belonging to the Basement Complex, which are usually at shallow depth. At some places intrusions, mostly granitic dykes are found which form outstanding ridges trending in general between northern and north direction (Lebon and Robertson 1961). The catchment area extends about 90 km upstream of Nyala in north – north – west direction, with an area of approximately 1360 km². The highest elevation of the Nyala Valley catchment reaches approximately 1100 m. The slope is gentle, changing from 6 m/km in the upper reaches of the catchment to about 3.8 m/km in the lower reaches. The upstream branches and width is 100 – 400 m at Nyala town. Downstream from Nyala the valley flow is divided into several branches and the width is reduced; flooding of the banks occurs regularly. The width of the Nyala valley is never more than 100 meters, until Nyala town is reached. There the width increases to a maximum of 400 meters. The present width of the wadi at Nyala town and further downstream is in places larger than ten years ago. This can be deduced from aerial photography, which dates back to 1972. Also in other valleys e.g. Wadi Bulbul, an increase in width is observed. The cause is probably that peak flows have increased, due to the advance of the denudation in the catchment area. The valley's catchment usually has a bed composed of a few meter coarse sands. In the beginning of the flood season infiltration into these sands will reduce the flood size. Later, after recharge has taken place this affect will be reduced.

Figure 6: Nyala valley lengths
Source: GIS Arc-Map 10.5 based on DEM 90 USGS

Rainfall characteristics over the two valleys

Gash valley lies within semi-arid climate of Sudan, with moderate amounts of rainfall during summer season. Nyala valley lies within belt of wet-climate in Sudan with abundant rainfall amounts during summer season. The I.T.C.Z which brings wet southwest winds over the Sudan influences both valleys' rainfall amounts. The Indian Ocean influences the climate of the Ethiopian plateau and the interior of the Sudan where in several years abundant rainfall amounts were observed over the Ethiopian plateau and southern Darfur. Rainfall was locally heavy (> 75 mm) in Southern Darfur regions of Sudan and abundant amounts of rain (> 100 mm) fell across the highlands regions of Ethiopia. These rains have kept river water levels elevated to or near flood level for the Blue and White Nile, Atbara River and Gash River (USAID 2010). The area including Gash valley indicates to a fewer rainfall amounts compared to that of Nyala valley's. Abundance rainfalls over the Ethiopian plateau influence the final budget of water of Gash's, while the Nyala valley's catchment area is determined and governed mainly by the local thunderstorms, which are usually travelling across the area from north-east to south-west. The storms usually cover only part of the catchment area, but the high intensity of the rains still generate considerable volumes of surface runoff.

Nyala rainfall station shows strong negative trend of declines in the 1940s or 1950s, which were years of high rainfall. By the early 1960s and that continued through the late 1960s, there was no gradual trend of decline in rainfall (Kevane et al., 2008). For the period 1940–1972, rainfall fluctuated around a stable mean, and for the period 1972–2002 rainfall again fluctuated around a stable but lower mean while the variance of rainfall was the same for both time periods. Simple regression analysis indicated to no statistically significant trend for the two time periods of 1940–1972 and 1972–2002 when considered separately. Very similar patterns emerged when only looking at duration and begging of the rainy season and for rainfall totals during July–August–September which are strong to the cutoffs in what constitutes **descent** rainfall (Kevane et al. 2008).

Hydrologic behavior of the two Valleys

The discharge measurements of the Gash River, which go back to 1907 (Figure 6), are showing high fluctuation. The minimum annual total discharge is 140 million m^3 , which was recorded in 1921, while the maximum annual discharge is 1430 million m^3 recorded in 1983. It should be noted that year 1983 represents the year before the peak of the drought in 1984, which stroke the whole African countries during the eighties, in particularly Ethiopia and Sudan. It is clear that the maximum annual flow is almost 10 times the minimum one, indicating the high variability of the flows in Gash River. However, the minimum instantaneous discharge is 170 m^3/s in 1921 and the maximum one is 870 m^3/s in 1983. The flow in the Gash Valley can start with only trickle move and reaches more than 850 m^3/s in very short time (Figure 7).

The annual average flow is 680 million m^3 (Bashar 2011), while the average annual discharge of the Gash Valley is estimated to be $1,056 \times 10^6 m^3$ at El Gera gage station (upstream) and $587 \times 10^6 m^3$ at Salam-Alikum gage station (downstream). The annual water loss mounts up to 40% of the total discharge which is attributed to infiltration and evapotranspiration.

Figure 7: Annual Total and Annual Maximum Flow Series of Gash River
Source: Bashar (2011)

The groundwater input reaches $386.11 \times 10^6 m^3/year$, while the groundwater output is calculated as $365.98 \times 10^6 m^3/year$. The estimated difference between the input and output water quantities in the upper and middle parts of the Gash Valley demonstrates a positive groundwater budget by about $20 \times 10^6 m^3/year$ (Eltom et al. 2010). Hydraulic conductivity ranges from 36 to 105 m/day, whereas the transmissivity ranges from 328 to 1,677 m^2/day . The monitoring of groundwater level measurements indicates that the water table rises during the rainy season by 9 m in the upstream and 6 m in the midstream areas. The storage capacity of the upper and middle parts of the Gash valley is calculated as $502 \times 10^6 m^3$. The average saturated thickness varies from 20-35 m. The predominance of sheet-flood deposits is consistent with the ephemeral flashy high flow regime in the Gash Valley. The recharge of aquifer is due to infiltration from the Gash Valley during flood seasons or direct precipitation from the rainfall. The general flow direction is towards the northwest (ELKirail et al. 2008). The infiltration capacity of the soil is low, due to the presence of a resistance surface soil cap. Soon after rain starts, the heavy impact of the raindrops close the soil surface almost completely, by the forming of a thin layer pan or cap.

Nyala valley runoff develops quickly soon after rain has started and then the valley is transformed into a wide, wild flowing stream, carrying large quantities of sediment and big logs and sometimes trees float down the river. The tremendous flow velocities (up to 5 m/s) and accompanying turbulences made it impossible to carry out discharge measurements. Under conditions of lower discharges, the maximum flow velocities measured reached 2.4 m/s. The water flows along small drainage channels, which are very densely distributed in a dendritic pattern. These join to form small wadi's which have a thin sandy bed, but no great lengths. Finally the water will reach one of the two main branches of the Nyala Valley, the wadi Kabris and the wadi Domai. The runoff decreases because of the flooding, but also by the infiltration into the subsurface. In this area the course of the Wadi is sometimes changed after a big flood has passed. As a consequence the old channel receives less water or even remains dry during the next floods. The valley bed, consisting of loose sands is very unstable, due flashy nature of the floods. The valley is capable of transporting large quantities of sediments and along its course is areas of erosion and sedimentation which continuously shifts after one flood at a certain location, bed levels might be lowered while after the next flood, the deposition of sediment can result in a higher elevation of the bed.

Comparisons of Hydro-geomorphic characteristics of the two valleys

Gash and Nyala valleys have summer rains which are more abundant in Nyala valley than Gash valley, both being influenced by I.T.C.Z. and plateaus of Ethiopia and Jebel Merra. Nyala valley exceeded Gash valley trice by longitudinal extension and twice by latitudinal extension. Gash's catchment area exceeded Nyala's

by 19,640 km² which equals 6.08% of the total catchment area for both valleys (Table1). The two valleys are similar in lower limit of width however; Nyala valley had an increase in width at its down reaching. They differ in the upper limit of width where Gash valley is twice that of Nyala valley. Nyala valley's elevation over mean sea level is double that of Gash's valley and expectedly more flash floods. Downstream from Nyala town the wadi flow is divided into several branches and similarly Gash valley which fans out into an inland delta while Nyala valley discharge into Bahr El-Arab river. The Gash valley is filled by the Quaternary alluvial deposits, unconformably overlying the basement rocks with predominance of sheet-flood deposits while the bigger valleys in the catchment of Nyala valley usually have a bed composed of a few meter coarse sands. Gash valley fluvial sediments revealed channel-fill and sheet-flood sequences and their thickness reaches 30 meters in upstream and 70 meters downstream and the clay of the plain is usually found above the river flood plain east and west of alluvial deposits and its sediments show some similarities and differences to those of ephemeral and low-sinuosity braided streams. There was non-conformity of the River Gash depositional style with the braided model of fluvial deposition. The infiltration capacity of the soil is low in Nyala valley compared with Gash valley.

In Gash valley maximum annual flow is almost 10 times the minimum one, indicating the high variability of the flows while the runoff is generated in Nyala valley by the rainfall in the catchment area and develops quickly; the wadi is then transformed into a wide, wild flowing river and the water flows along small drainage channels, which are very densely distributed in a dendritic pattern, the course of the Wadi is sometimes changed after a big flood has passed. As a consequence the old channel receives less water or even remains dry during the next floods. Gash discharge measurements are showing high fluctuation and the flow can start with only trickle move and reaches more than 850 m³/s in a very short period of time. The annual loss mounts up to 40% of the total discharge and the estimated difference between the input and output of water quantities in the upper and middle parts of the River Gash Basin demonstrates a positive groundwater budget by about 20×10^6 m³/year.

Table1: Hydro-geomorphic Comparisons between Gash and Nyala valleys

Gash valley	Nyala valley
<p>Located at 36° 15' - 36° 30' E, and 15° 15' - 15° 45' N</p> <p>Extends quarter a longitudinal degree.</p> <p>Extends half a latitudinal degree</p> <p>The catchment area is 21000 km²</p> <p>The range of width is 100-800.</p> <p>Elevation is 500 m.s.l.</p> <p>Predominance of sheet-flood deposits is consistent with the ephemeral flashy high flow regime.</p> <p>Filled by the Quaternary alluvial deposits, formed by the action of Gash Valley during the flood seasons, unconformably overlying the basement rocks. Detailed facies analysis of the River Gash fluvial sediments has revealed a number of facies and two distinct types of sequences: channel-fill and sheet-flood sequences. The clay of the plain is usually found above the river flood plain east and west of alluvial deposits. The thickness of alluvial deposits upstream is about 30 meters and reach up to 70 meters downstream.</p> <p>Maximum annual flow is almost 10 times the minimum one, indicating the high variability and fluctuation.</p> <p>The non-conformity of the River Gash depositional style with the braided model of fluvial deposition may be due to this semi-arid terminal flashy character which has control on the depositional processes and patterns.</p> <p>Sediments show some similarities and differences to those of ephemeral and low-sinuosity braided streams.</p> <p>The flow can start with only trickle move and reaches more than 850 m³/s in very short time. The annual loss mounts up to 40% of the total discharge.</p> <p>Moderate amounts of rainfall during summer season influenced by I.T.C.Z. and Ethiopian plateau.</p>	<p>Located at 24° 30' - 25° 15' E, and 11° 45' - 12° - 45' N.</p> <p>Extends three quarters a longitudinal degree.</p> <p>Extends a complete latitudinal degree.</p> <p>The catchment area is 1360 km².</p> <p>The range of width is 100-400.</p> <p>Elevation is 1100 m.s.l.</p> <p>The bigger valleys in the catchment usually have a bed composed of a few meter coarse sands.</p> <p>Downstream from Nyala town the wadi flow is divided into several branches and the width is reduced; flooding of the banks occurs regularly.</p> <p>The present width of the wadi at Nyala town and further downstream is in places larger than ten years ago. Also in other valleys, e.g. Wadi Bulbul, an increase in width is observed. The cause is probably that peak flows have increased, due to the advance of the denudation in the catchment area.</p> <p>The infiltration capacity of the soil is low, due to the presence of a resistance surface soil cap.</p> <p>The runoff is generated by the rainfall in the catchment area and develops quickly; the wadi is then transformed into a wide, wild flowing river.</p> <p>The water flows along small drainage channels, which are very densely distributed in a dendritic pattern. These join to form small wadi's which have a thin sandy bed, but no great lengths. In this area the course of the Wadi is sometimes changed after a big flood has passed. As a consequence the old channel receives less water or even remains dry during the next floods.</p> <p>Abundant rainfall amounts during summer season influenced by I.T.C.Z., Jebel Merra and local thunderstorms.</p>

Discussion

Gash and Nyala valleys lie at different latitudes and longitudes, but they are of mountainous origin, flashy with high discharge initiated by similar rainfall influences. They are integral part of the network of Sudanese rivers and valleys (DIU 2009). Sudan is an agricultural country with huge fertile lands and strives to optimize utilization of its share of Nile Water Agreement with Egypt to achieve and accelerate development in riverain areas of central and northern Sudan where Gas and Kassala areas are at a distance. Alternative development efforts could target developing and promoting water harvesting of Gas and Nyala valleys to provide huge amounts of water that might exceed some areas close to the Niles. They would participate into developing water sources outside the Nile areas, reducing poverty of rural communities, enhancing agro-animal production through provisioning of quality water, conserving and protecting the environment, enhancing national security and promoting peace and settlement by developing border areas and reducing water related conflicts throughout Sudan and neighboring countries, increasing per capita share of home water in line with the State's strategy in supplying quality water with sufficient quantity. They could specifically contribute into settlement of nomads to evade their conflict with peasants, and encourage refugees and internally displaced peoples to return home (DIU 2009). This is particularly significant since the areas of Gash and Nyala valleys are characterized by climatic conditions conducive to water shortage which had seriously caused many dramatic changes by disturbing the rhythms of grazing, cultivation, and migration and so compete with livestock for both land and water (Alredaisy 2012).

The Gash and Nyala are factual parts of areas of tribal and militant conflicts in Sudan. The East Front and Militant Groups in Darfur fought the Ingaz Government for decades. The initiation of tribal conflicts, prior to their politicalization, was environmentally based on shear water resources during the dry season. Implementation of water harvesting programs based on hydrological potentialities of Nyala valleys could provide reliable sources of water for rural communities and support the State's policy to achieve "Darfur's comprehensive peace" (DIU 2009). This is similarly expected by the Gash valley in Eastern Sudan, to engine targeting collecting rain water or "seizure" of flowing water during the rainy season during December- June for human and animals announced by Water Harvesting Programs of Sudan. This is important under the scenario of climate change and related anthropogenic effects in the Sahelian zone of Sudan where Kassala and Nyala areas are part of that zone. Under this climate change conditions, shortage in water production is expected, which will be more exacerbated by increasing human and animal demands. This is important to put into consideration with World Health Organization (WHO 1983) of daily allocation of per capita water, but the inclusion of animal population gives a different scene of water shortage.

Both areas witnessed onsets of desertification as it has been designated by the United Nations as under "very high risk" of desertification (UN 1977), desert encroachment, and threat from sand creep and have been affected by changing characteristics of the rainy season since early sixties (Zeng 2003). The rainfall records of many gauge stations suggest a long-term average annual rainfall of 285 mm (1902-1990), and since the 1950s the average rainfall has fallen sharply due to severe drought from 1968 to 1972 and again in the 1980s, with 1984 being the driest year on record. The mean rainfall for 1965-84 was 214 mm, 40% lower than the 365 mm seen from 1920-39 (Walsh 1991). The decade 1981-90 was 35% below the mean of 330 mm for 1920-50. Based upon available figures there seems to be little evidence for significant improvement since 1990 (Alredaisy and Davies 2000). Rainfall figures in the 20th century suggest that the 1930s saw a peak in rainfall and that since then rainfall was generally in decline until the mid-1970s, when it appears to have leveled out at about 250 mm. These areas also face problems of global warming, rapid increase of human and animal population as manifested by deterioration of natural vegetation (Davies 1987). In such marginal lands of Kassala and Nyala, water insecure groups of the Sudan are found, who are usually poor and self-provisioning producers (Green 1989, Knerr 1998) and are pushed by land hunger into ever more marginal lands in term of weather, soil and ecological fragility (Alredaisy and Davies 2001).

The importance of water harvesting of Gash and Nyala valleys could extend to include reduction and management of urban disaster for Kassala and Nyala central-regional towns. They are both extremely vulnerable to flashy annual floods which caused damages and sometimes lead to population displacement (Alredaisy 2011). Urban disaster management and reduction strategy for both of them, the inclusion of the concept of regional flood vulnerability is a necessary perquisite. It concerns with the capacity to resist flood of all kinds of disaster bearers at a region, and includes indicators of disaster environment, disaster drivers, disaster bearers, and disaster bearing capacity of society (GAO et al 2004). Comprehensive evaluation of urban disaster reduction management is important prerequisites for improving the level of urban disaster

reduction management in Kassala and Nyala towns. Following the future strategies of world disaster reduction in 2005, it could be more effective. These strategies, which are a core task of regional sustainable development, include “construction of community disaster-reduction system, combining disaster reduction with regional development to seek the sustainable development way and to build up safer community systems which can accept some certain risk level. it is important to establish warning systems, accelerate to share disaster reduction information and make full use of the existing disaster reduction resources in order to establish a social-economic system which can coexist with disaster risks well ” (Shi Pei-jun et al. 2005).

Conclusions and recommendations

The main findings of this research are that,

- 1- Geomorphological characteristics of Gash and Nyala valleys are almost identical.
- 2- They are of mountainous origin and although differ in geographic locations; both are influenced by the Intertropical convergence Zone (ITCZ) and Indian Ocean monsoons which initiate their annual flooding.
- 3- Both valleys are flashy with huge annual discharge and almost similar hydrological behavior.
- 4- They are source of disaster vulnerability to Kassala and Nyala regional towns and their geographic neighborhood.
- 5- They are proficiently potential to contribute into rural community development in semi arid Sudan in the course of appropriate water harvesting programs. This could eventually reduce vulnerability to flood disasters in their geographic neighborhoods.

The optimization of hydro-geomorphic characteristics for water harvesting and disaster management of Gash and Nyala valleys to induce rural community development, drives for recommendation of the improvement of hydrological recording and geomorphic controls on hydrology at the scale of Gash and Nyala valleys and at the scale of their physiographic regions. This is important since geomorphology exerts both direct and indirect controls on the pattern, timing and volume of runoff generated within a basin. At the scale of physiographic regions, the natural flow regime of both valleys is determined by the broad scale interaction between geology and climate which establishes the overall pattern of annual runoff, drainage network structure and the longitudinal organization of the two valleys drainage. This is important since will determine the timing and rate of runoff for individual storm events, which are necessary for disaster management. Improvement of spatial estimates of precipitation for water harvesting and disaster management is also important. They could be computed from point measurements using well established spatial interpolation techniques. Also, estimating the spatial and temporal distribution of runoff entering the two valleys' system during a storm event is important to the understanding of the physical dynamics of catchment hydrology (Refsgaard et al. 1995). This is beside recharge estimates including physical, chemical or numerical modeling methods (Lerner et al., 1990; Scanlon et al. 2007), and flow rate estimates or water level in the channel system by using one-dimensional modeling system (Havnø et al. 1995).

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